

MAJOR EVENTS IN BRAZIL: Socioeconomic and cultural developments due to the 2014 World Cup in the Federal District (DF)

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Abstract

The main objective of this article was to analyze the major events in Brazil, having as a case study the 2014 FIFA World Cup, held in Brasília/DF. The development of this article is in line with interviews with the target audience, which emphasize the participation of researchers, for a better understanding of the context of the chosen city. Among the main results, in addition to conducting field research aimed at residents of Brasília/DF, where data was gathered, thus generating a result about the event. Together with these results and from the point of view of its population, it was verified the legacy that the 2014 COPA event will leave for Brasília after 2014

Keywords: Brasília. Events. FIFA World Cup. Soccer.

INTRODUCTION

Presenting yourself to the world in front of a new reality. The image of Brazil as a country needs to expand outside the Rio-São Paulo axis. The federal capital, built in the 20th century, has not yet hosted a large-scale global event.

The World Cup is the opportunity to introduce different cultures and give visibility to the city of Brasília/DF and the Central Plateau, as the city has prepared and transformed to host the event as well as how it has opened up to the world.

This article aims to describe, in particular, the socioeconomic and cultural developments that the aforementioned football championship may provide about the economy, infrastructure, and tourism, among other important sectors, in the city of Brasília/DF.

METHODS

Descriptive, exploratory research with a qualitative approach was carried out. Initially, a bibliographical review was carried out, raising theoretical conceptions of several authors for a better understanding of the topic at hand.

The next phase included field research carried out with the population of Brasília/DF to obtain data to analyze the impacts of the 2014 FIFA Cup in that city.

The method used for the sample was the non-probabilistic one, being a single purposeful sampling procedure, as the research subjects – the population residing in the city of Brasília/DF – were intentionally chosen, and 20 people participated.

The questionnaire applied presented a total of 10 (ten) questions, divided into 2 (two) parts. The first part collected the informant's profile, consisting of 3 (three) questions in a set of closed-options (dichotomous) responses.

The second part presented 7 (seven) open questions related to the perception of citizens residing in Brasília/DF about the 2014 World Cup for subsequent content analysis (BARDIN, 2004)

RESULTS

The host city selected for the case study

was Brasília (FIGURE 1), which is the Federal Capital of the Federative Republic of Brazil and seat of government of the Federal District, making it the fourth most populous city in Brazil.

FIGURE 1 – Images from Brasília/DF

Source: Google Imagens (2013)

Brasília is located in the Center-West region of the country, along the geographic region known as the Central Plateau. The following is a summary of the main data from the DF:

Table 1 – Summary of the Main Data of DF in the 2010 Census

FEDERAL DISTRICT	
Capital	Brasília
Population estimated 2013	2.789,761
Population 2010	2.570,160
Área (km ²)	2.799,999
Demographic Density hab/km ²	444,66
Number of municipalities	1

Source: IBGE (2013)

FIGURE 2 Brasília's National Stadium Mané Garrincha

Source: Brasília at the worldcup (2013)

The tourism field, on the other hand, is what will bring more significant changes by placing the DF on the mandatory route for tourism, as it has a differentiated attraction which is its architectural set. And about the hotel sector, Brasília had, in 2010, the number 50 hotels, with a total of 28 thousand beds. To meet the demand for the World Cup, the Financial Supervision and Control Commission, Subcommittee on Supervision of the 2014 World Cup, with their studies, predicted a 20% increase in the number of beds available to meet the demand, which means building and delivering in the minimum more 5,600 beds (BRASIL, 2010).

Currently, the Federal District has 2,606,885 inhabitants and boasts an HDI-M of 0.875, the highest in Brazil, with a GDP of R\$89,630,109.00, which makes it the host of the 2014 World Cup.

As for age, 20 informants divided into groups of four age groups were evaluated: 18 to 30 years; 31 to 49 years old; 50 to 65 years old and over 65 years old. In the research, the sample equivalent to the 2nd group (TABLE 2) was predominant.

Table 2 – Most frequent age of informants

Age	N° of informants	%
18 a 30 years	5	25
31 a 49 years	10	50
50 a 65 years	3	15
above the 65 years	2	10
total		100

Source: Author data (2013)

The sample consisted of 20 volunteers, of which 16 (80%) were male and 4 (20%) were female, as shown below (GRAPH 1).

Graph 1 - Percentage by gender

■ Masculino
■ Feminino

Source: Author data (2013)

When analyzing the studied sample about gender, males predominated in this research (80%), despite the methodological care taken to ensure an adequate sample of the population, in disagreement with the results of the research carried out in the same city by Marinho; Hammann and Lima (2007).

Regarding the length of residence in Brasília, the evaluated informants were divided into four groups: 1 to 10 years; 11 to 25 years; 26 to 40 years old and over 40 years old. Samples equivalent to the 2nd and 3rd groups predominated in the research (TABLE 3).

Table 3 – Residence time in the city

Age	N° of informants	%
1 a 10 years	2	10
11 a 25 years	9	45
26 a 40 years	9	45
above the 40 years	0	0
total		100

Source: Author data (2013)

According to (MARINHO; HAMMANN ELIMA, 2007), a characteristic of Brasília is that it has a population originating from different regions of the country. The sampling process that was used in this research guarantees population representativeness for the Federal District.

About the main challenges for Brasília to operationalize a Soccer World Cup with

quality, some answers were selected in which the interviewees answered:

a) "Mobility, Safety, Health, Communication".

b) "Improve public transport, airport, security and the city's hotel network".

c) "Improve the organization, infrastructure, security scheme, traffic, public transport for the event, airport and hotel sector".

d) "Quality stadiums to host events of this magnitude, that is, with comfort, sufficient and clean restrooms, easy access, numbered seats with reserved tickets, among other things; mobility facility airport-hotel, hotel-airport, hotel-stadium, and vice versa, and security so that people feel at ease when moving through the city, without running the risk of being robbed or of any other type of aggression".

e) "Improving infrastructure, security, transport, and signaling".

It is observed in the volunteers' responses that the item "safety" appears first.

From a socio-economic point of view, some interviewees described the advantages that can be expected for the City of hosting an event such as the Soccer World Cup, such as:

The likely improvements for the population as a whole".

Improvements that will be carried out in the city to support the event, such as Improvement in the hotel network and the Expansion and modernization of the Juscelino Kubitschek International Airport in Brasília, restoration of the city's streets and avenues, Infrastructure works, and actions to encourage local tourism and the training of professionals are also among the investments that are intended to be made".

It will bring benefits to various sectors such as restaurants, hotels, shopkeepers and the generation of several jobs and income for the community".

That there is a legacy for the city in this aspect, that is, after the event, what was invested starts to revert as a gain for society.

For example, the arena is economically exploited for other events (shows, football matches, exhibitions, fairs, etc.); the

transport system remains with the same quality presented during the Cup; the airport will continue to offer the same type of disservice presented during the World Cup and public safety will be permanent, that is, it will not only act in big events".

"Increase in tourism, tax collection, and trade growth".

According to the interviewees' speech, there seems to be a lot of concern for real benefits to occur that serve the population of Brasília. Among the several cited, it is interesting to mention Melo (2011) when highlighting the proposal directly concerning social aspects, for example, the eradication of illiteracy in the territory of the Federal District. By 2014, about 65,000 people are intended to be literate, approximately 3.5% of the population.

Another important social factor raised with the 2014 World Cup is jobs that emerged during the infrastructure works and those that will remain after the event (MELO, 2011).

Regarding the interference of the World Cup in the quality of life of the population of Brasília, some resident volunteers responded that:

It will increase people's self-esteem in holding and participating in an event of such magnitude".

On the days of the games there will be a worsening of traffic, in addition to political demonstrations that will disrupt the city, but there will be positive points with the improvement of services and quality of restaurants, bars, hotels, cultural attractions, and tours to monuments, and tourist attractions that will be available to the tourists arriving in the capital".

Ribeiro (2012) claims that the 2014 World Cup revealed the need for large investments so that the planned events can take place successfully. In this sense, the construction of several works is planned in Brasília, which are in progress, in the implementation phase or already concluded. Regarding the infrastructure for tourism, today, 50 hotels with a total of 28 thousand beds are available. The forecast is that the offer will increase by at least 20% by 2014 (BRASIL, 2010).

About the considerations about what will be done to facilitate the access of the

population of the City without privileged financial conditions to the event, some selected interviewees answered:

Nothing, at most a few dozen chairs in the worst places”.

Following the events of the Confederations Cup held in 2013, unfortunately, I don't believe that anything will be done so that less privileged populations can participate in the 2014 World Cup”. In my opinion, nothing will be done, because so far no one has taken any action about it.”

This type of event is not made with this population in mind. It is a commercial event, where large sums of money are invested and which the return is sought. Hence, this population will benefit from what is positively the legacy of the Cup: transport, security, employment, etc.”.

It was announced in the press that the organization of the Cup will reserve tickets for distribution in schools and public entities”.

From the speech of the selected interviewees, it is possible to observe the lack of credibility about the access of low-income people to official games, such as what happened in the 2013 Confederations Cup, in which a large portion of fans from the Brazilian elite.

As for the observations on the interventions that have been carried out in the current sports infrastructure in Brasília due to the 2014 World Cup, some of the chosen responses were:

That I know, nothing”.

Only the construction of the New Football Stadium “Brasilia National Stadium – formerly Mané Garrincha” is the great sporting infrastructure built for the 2014 World Cup, the teams that come here to play should use the sporting establishments that already exist in the city for their training, but nothing is being done for the city's sports infrastructure as far as I know”.

“As this is a World Cup event, an ultra-modern stadium was built following the international standard of technology and infrastructure that is already adopted in other international stadiums”.

Especially in transport, there should be a large investment, as the city has always

lacked it. Transport in Brasilia is insufficient and expensive. If the number of bus lines and also the number of buses per line are expanded, it is already a beautiful legacy. The subway, as it is more expensive and takes a long time to build, will certainly not undergo any changes”.

Many concerns were observed in the respondents' answers regarding the interventions that have been carried out in the current infrastructure in Brasília due to the 2014 World Cup, and not only those related to sports infrastructure.

Informants were asked what they believed would be the main legacies that are being planned for the Federal District after the 2014 World Cup, and the responses selected were:

For now, after the Confederations Cup, I only see the stadium and the hotel chain”.

According to Isto é magazine (2013, p.1), “the World Cup plays a vital role in the transformation of the Federal District”. A survey carried out by the Getúlio Vargas Foundation estimated at R\$ 4 billion the amount to be spent by Brazilian and foreign tourists who intend to visit the capital during the event.

CONCLUSION

The importance of carrying out large events is a window of opportunity for the city or locality that hosts a global event. Brasília showed that it is possible to improve the image of the FIFA World Cup - Brazil 2014 event, even with unfinished or postulated works for dates still uncertain.

In this desideratum, the authorities must think and rethink strategies to reproduce the best way to expose the city in large events so that the country's image bears good results and can attract tourists, events, and, above all, trade. One cannot give the impression that the investment is wasted on pharaonic or unfinished works, which goes against the auspices of sustainable development in force in today's world.

It should be noted that today's world demands quality practices for major events and the responsibility of the organizers, which is why the opportunity to show Brasília to the world was built on works with a gigantic context that accompany the city's history. However, the debate imposed

concerns the allocation of resources and their destination, which matters in strategic decisions that effectively reach the well-being of the population of Brasilia and not for the simple delight of tourists who bring ephemeral and non-permanent profits to the city from which the legacy can be most questioned.

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